

Integrating Computer Animation in Teaching of Chemical Bonding: Effect on Students' Achievement

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of computer animation in teaching of chemical bonding on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Ogbia Local Government of Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 865 chemistry students from 30 public secondary schools. Taro Yamane formula was used to draw a sample size of 243 SS 1 chemistry students from four secondary schools. The instrument used for data collection was Chemical Bonding Achievement Test (CBAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three research experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.80 was obtained. The researchers facilitated a comprehensive two-week training programme within the schools, specifically tailored for the regular chemistry teachers. This program was designed to enhance their instructional skills, familiarize them with innovative teaching strategies, and improve their overall effectiveness in delivering chemistry lessons. The chemistry teachers for the experimental group used computer animation while the teachers for the control group used the conventional teaching method. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that students who were taught chemical bonding by integrating computer animation in the teaching process recorded increased achievement than their counterparts who were taught with the lecture method. The test of hypotheses also showed that the mean difference in achievement was significant, in favour of the students in the experimental group. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that the government should provide chemistry teachers with computer facilities such as computers, storage devices and projectors which they need for preparing and teaching their lessons using computer animation.

Keywords: Computer Animation, Chemical Bonding, Academic Achievement

Introduction

Science represents humanity's efforts to investigate, explore, interpret, and interact with the materials and forces of the universe. No nation can achieve its peak in technology or development without prioritizing the teaching and learning of science. The field of science is divided into branches such as earth sciences, life sciences, and physical sciences. Chemistry, a branch of physical science, focuses on the composition, properties, reactions, and structure of matter. The significance of chemistry in daily life cannot be overstated. According to

Ababio (2017), chemistry is defined as a pure science subject that explores the composition, structure, properties, and transformations of matter, along with its practical applications in everyday life and industrial processes. It is a vital branch of science and serves as a foundation for many professional courses in the science field. According to Igwe (2017), chemistry primarily focuses on non-living matter. Jegede (2012) emphasized that chemistry is universally relevant to human development, particularly in equipping students with knowledge applicable to real-life situations. Despite its complexity, chemistry holds a crucial place in the Nigerian Senior Secondary School curriculum.

Chemistry plays a crucial role in technological advancement. Asiyai (2015) noted that the principles of chemistry have significantly contributed to the development of modern technology through their application to various inventions. The study of chemistry remains vital to humanity, as it provides explanations for natural phenomena and everyday processes such as the burning of firewood, cooking, rusting of nails, fermentation, and the spontaneous emission of radiation by certain elements. Galvez (2018) highlighted that molecular models, simulations, and animations can enhance the learning of chemistry, particularly in improving understanding of concepts like chemical bonding.

Chemical bonding is a topic in Senior Secondary One (SS1) revised chemistry curriculum. It is an important concept in the teaching and learning of chemistry at all levels of schooling. Chemical bonding is a key concept in chemistry. Chemical bonding theories and models are central to other topics taught in chemistry curricula. Chemical bonding is a concept in which understanding is developed by using models through which the students are expected to interpret a disparate range of symbolic representations (Taber & Coll, 2012). Chemical bonding is a central concept in the teaching of chemistry and therefore a thorough understanding of it is essential for understanding almost every other areas of chemistry, such as carbon compounds, proteins, polymers, acid and bases, chemical energy and thermodynamics. Franz and Harkerat (2010) reported that students have problem with understanding of chemical bonding. According to Franz and Harkerat (2010), knowledge in chemistry is based on students' understanding of basic principles. The traditional approach of using lecture method alone may not be adequate.

Teaching – learning process is the heart of education. The use of the traditional lecture method for teaching all topics in chemistry has been found to be counter-productive and resulting in poor achievement in chemistry in external examination (WAEC, 2015-2018: Oloruntegbe & Odutuyi, 2015). Okoyefi & Nzewi (2013) opined that students perform well when they are exposed to methods that interest them during the teaching-learning process. With the advent of the Internet and the multiple formats that can be communicated over the World Wide Web, teachers now have several new and exciting ways to present information. The Web allows the incorporation of animation, moving pictures, and sound into lessons, which extends ones abilities to present materials that encourage student interaction with the subject matter. In a lesson on chemical bonding, an application could involve demonstrating how ionic and covalent bonds are essential in the formation of common compounds, such as sodium chloride (table salt) and water. For example, students can analyze the practical uses of sodium chloride in food preservation and water in sustaining life, emphasizing how the type of bonding influences the properties and functions of these compounds in secondary schools.

Many secondary school students struggle to grasp certain concepts in chemistry (WAEC Chief Examiner's Report, 2019). Statistics reveal a persistent trend of mass failure in chemistry

examinations, with student performance steadily declining over time (Danjuma, 2015). The poor achievement of students in chemistry at the SSCE level has been linked to several factors, including the negative attitudes of both teachers and learners toward the subject, the extensive chemistry curriculum, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient instructional materials, and mathematical challenges faced by both students and teachers (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2019). While past efforts to address these challenges have largely focused on improving conventional teaching methods, little attention has been given to adopting innovative approaches, such as integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT), particularly the use of computer animations, into chemistry instruction.

Computer animation is a general term for a visual digital display technology that stimulates moving objects on screen. Computer animation is traditionally defined as an inanimate entity that appears to take on dynamic attributes such as movement, growth and speech which are normally associated with living organisms (Ploatzner & Lowe, 2012). Computer animation has been educationally defined by Lander and Lunderstorm (2013) as a set of varying images presented dynamically according to users' action in ways that help the user perceive a continuous change over time and develop a more appropriate mental model of a task. Basak, Yucehan and Ahmet (2018) described animation as an effective learning tool that attracts attention, engages learner, and sustains motivation and enhance retention of concepts that results in meaningful learning. It has been shown from several research reports such as Kasali (2015) and Wishart (2014) that animations as technological tools used in education have contributed a lot to the students' fulfillment of cognitive function. Aneke and Opara (2021) found that students who were taught chemical bonding using animation outperformed and retained the concept of chemical bonding than those taught using lecture method. An example of animation could be likened to Mickey Mouse, an entertainment programme where inanimate objects perform functions of human beings.

Animations in chemistry topics can visually represent molecular interactions, chemical reactions, or concepts like atomic structure and bonding, making complex ideas more accessible to learners. To create such animations, software like Blender, ChemDraw, or Maya can be used, as they allow for detailed modeling and animation of chemical structures and processes. Specialized training in 3D modeling, animation techniques, and familiarity with chemical visualization tools is essential to produce accurate and engaging animations for educational purposes. A study conducted by Ikwuka and Samuel (2017), showed that Computer Animation Chemistry Instruction (CACI) had significant effect on students' academic achievement in Chemistry; and that gender had significant effect on the academic achievement in Chemistry of male and female students who were taught CACI in favour of males. Njoku and Eze-Odurukwe (2015) indicated that students' academic achievements are greatly improved when taught with computer animations.

Academic achievement refers to the extent to which a student has successfully reached their short- or long-term educational objectives. It encompasses the knowledge gained and skills developed during schooling (Vein, Parveen, Syed & Nazir, 2013). According to Ejesi (2014), academic achievement represents the outcomes of education, reflecting how well a student, teacher, or institution has met their educational goals. Hanushek, Rivkin, and Kain (2015) further described academic achievement as the level of success an individual demonstrates in examinations, showcasing their abilities and understanding of the subject matter. However, studies by Gull and Shehzad (2015) highlight that students' academic

performance in various aspects of science remains poor, regardless of gender differences, emphasizing the need for more effective instructional strategies.

Another variable of interest in this study is gender because it is a determinant factor of learning. Gender is the range of characteristics pertaining to, and differentiating between femininity and masculinity. According to Okeke (2010), gender is referred to as socially constructed roles and socially learned behaviours and expectations associated with males and females. Gender according Onyeonoru (2015), is referred to as the differentiation in roles between men and women which is different from sex but construed by society through socialization.

Gender issues in chemistry and science in general is still controversial. Adeyegbe (2010) observed gender differences in achievement in both chemistry and other science subjects. Gongden & Gongden (2019) found that there is no significant difference in achievement in chemistry of boys and girls. Anagbogu & Ezeliora (2007), discovered that girls achieved higher than their male counterparts in sciences contrary to this, Adigwe (2014) observed that male students have higher academic achievement in chemistry than the females. Therefore, further studies are required to clarify the effect of different instructional strategies on academic achievement of boys and girls. It does appear that these gender differences in students' achievement vary with the method of instruction. One wonders whether the computer animation can equally be effective in teaching science subjects like Chemistry and their influence on gender.

Statement of the Problem

Students' performance in Chemistry has remained unsatisfactory over the years in Nigeria. This is largely due to the declining state of Chemistry teaching and learning in most secondary schools across the country, particularly in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, where many schools lack adequately equipped laboratories to support effective learning. This deficiency has contributed to consistently poor outcomes in Chemistry in the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE). Reports from external examination bodies such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) have consistently highlighted a steady decline in students' performance in the subject.

The persistent underachievement in Chemistry has raised concerns among stakeholders in secondary education. While Chemistry teachers have been making efforts to improve instructional methods, they have largely overlooked technology-driven approaches, such as the integration of computer animation. Research has shown that the use of computer animation in instructional delivery enhances students' understanding and academic performance in Chemistry. This raises the question of whether such a technique could also improve students' achievement in Chemistry in Ogbia Local Government Area. Therefore, the present study examined the effect of using computer animation in teaching chemical bonding on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of computer animation in teaching of chemical bonding on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Ogbia Local Government of Bayelsa State. The study specifically investigated the:

1. effect of computer animation on SS I Chemistry students' academic achievement when taught chemical bonding and those taught the same topic using lecture method;
2. influence of gender (male and female) on Chemistry students' academic achievement when taught chemical bonding using computer animation.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS I Chemistry students taught chemical bonding with computer animation and those taught the same topic using lecture method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female SS I Chemistry students taught chemical bonding with computer animation?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study and they were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS 1 Chemistry students taught chemical bonding using computer animation and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female SS 1 Chemistry students taught chemical bonding with computer animation.
- Ho₃:** There is no significant interaction effect of gender and computer animation on students' academic achievement in chemical bonding.

Research Method

The study adopted quasi-experimental design of the pre-test post-test non-equivalent group design. Quasi-experimental research design is defined as one which random assignment of subjects to experiment and control groups is not possible (Nworgu, 2015). The population for the study was 865 Senior Secondary School 1 (SS 1) chemistry students. Taro Yamane formula was used to draw a sample size of 243 SS 1 chemistry students. However, the number of chemistry students in the experimental group was 142 (81 males and 61 females), while there were 101 chemistry students in the control group drawn from 4 schools out of the 30 secondary schools. The instrument used for data collection was Chemical Bonding Achievement Test (CBAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three research experts. Chemical bond animation visually illustrates how atoms interact to form bonds, such as ionic, covalent, or metallic bonds, by showing electron sharing or transfer processes dynamically. The researchers developed and adapted it into the teaching by using animation software to create step-by-step representations of bonding, integrating them into lesson plans, and utilizing them as interactive tools to enhance students' understanding and engagement. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.82 was obtained. A two-week training session was organized within the schools by the researchers for the regular chemistry teachers. The chemistry teachers for the experimental group used computer animation while the teachers for the control group used the conventional teaching method. Mean and standard deviation were used for

answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results Presentation

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS I Chemistry students taught chemical bonding with computer animation and those taught the same topic using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught chemical bonding with computer animation and those taught using lecture method

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)
Experimental Group	142	46.71	14.86	72.61	19.54
Control Group	101	39.68	12.77	58.49	17.42
Total	243				

The table reveals the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of Chemistry students taught using computer animation (experimental group) and the lecture method (control group). The experimental group had higher pre-test and post-test mean scores (46.71 and 72.61, respectively) compared to the control group (39.68 and 58.49, respectively). Both groups showed an increase in mean scores from pre-test to post-test, indicating learning gains. However, the experimental group exhibited a larger improvement in mean scores (an increase of 25.90) compared to the control group (an increase of 18.81). The standard deviations suggest a slightly wider spread of scores in the experimental group post-test (19.54) than in the control group post-test (17.42), reflecting more variability in student performance.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female SS 1 Chemistry students taught chemical bonding with computer animation?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught chemical bonding using computer animation

Group	N	Pre-test mean	SD	Post-test mean	SD
Male	81	42.81	17.39	71.56	21.49
Female	61	34.66	14.39	63.78	18.41

The table presents the mean achievement scores and standard deviations (SD) of male and female SS1 Chemistry students before and after being taught chemical bonding using computer animation. For the male group (N=81), the pre-test mean was 42.81 (SD=17.39), which increased to a post-test mean of 71.56 (SD=21.49), indicating significant improvement.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of male and female Chemistry students taught chemical bonding using computer animation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	9464.494	2	4732.247	23.642	.000	Rejected
Intercept	5820.730	1	5820.730	29.080	.000	
Pretest	9438.592	1	9438.592			
GENDER	178.022	1	178.022	47.155	.000	
Error	31425.006	140	200.159	0.889	.147	
Total	434912.000	142				
Corrected Total	40889.500	141				

a. R Squared = .231 (Adjusted R Squared = .222)

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) presented in the table examines the mean achievement scores of male and female SS 1 Chemistry students taught chemical bonding using computer animation. The corrected model is significant with an F-value of 23.642 and a p-value of .000, indicating a significant effect of the independent variables. The gender variable is significant (F = 47.155, p = .000), suggesting a significant difference in achievement scores between male and female students. The R-squared value of .231 indicates that 23.1% of the variance in achievement scores is explained by the model. The null hypothesis (Ho2), which states there is no significant difference in achievement scores based on gender, is therefore rejected.

Ho3: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and computer animation on students' academic achievement in chemical bonding.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the interaction effect of gender and method (computer animation) on Chemistry students' achievement in chemical bonding

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	289.802	2	144.901	19.89	.00	Rejected
Intercept	2091.89	1	2091.89	1011.32	.00	
METHOD*GENDER	167.98	1	167.98	19.89	.02	
Error	5019.77	241	24.20	81.99	.03	
Total	14311.45	243				
Corrected Total	8901.89	242				

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) results in Table 5 reveal a significant interaction effect of gender and computer animation on Chemistry students' academic achievement in chemical bonding. The interaction effect (METHOD*GENDER) yielded an F-value of 19.89 with a p-value of 0.02, which is less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho3). This implies that the combination of gender and teaching method (computer animation) significantly influences students' academic performance in chemical bonding. The corrected

model also shows statistical significance ($F = 19.89, p < 0.05$), indicating that the model adequately explains the variation in academic achievement. Thus, the results suggest that gender interacts with the teaching method to impact learning outcomes in this context.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that computer animation significantly enhanced the achievement of secondary school chemistry students during lessons on chemical bonding compared to the lecture method. Male students outperformed their female counterparts in both the treatment and control groups. These findings align with the study by Aneke and Opara (2021), which concluded that students taught chemical bonding using animation demonstrated superior performance and retention of concepts compared to those taught through the lecture method.

Similarly, Njoku and Eze-Odurukwe (2015) affirmed that students' academic achievements are notably improved when computer animations are incorporated into teaching. Additionally, this study concurs with the findings of Ikwuka and Samuel (2017), who reported that computer animation significantly impacts students' academic achievement in Chemistry and that male students generally outperform their female peers. Furthermore, this study supports the observations of Adigwe (2014), who noted that male students tend to achieve higher academic success in Chemistry than female students. The consistent trend across these studies underscores the positive impact of computer animation on students' academic performance in Chemistry. It also highlights the gender disparities in achievement, with males often performing better than females in this subject area.

Conclusion

The use of computer animation as a teaching strategy for senior secondary school students proved to be more effective in improving students' achievement in chemistry than the traditional lecture method. This effectiveness was demonstrated by the superior performance of the experimental group, which was taught using computer animation, compared to the control group, which relied on the lecture method. The findings further highlighted that gender influenced the level of achievement among students. Male students who were taught using computer animation outperformed their female counterparts, showcasing a notable gender gap in achievement. This disparity suggests that while computer animation is a powerful tool for enhancing learning outcomes, it may affect male and female students differently. The results emphasize the need to consider gender dynamics in the implementation of innovative teaching strategies like computer animation to ensure equitable learning opportunities for all students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Bayelsa state government should provide chemistry teachers with computer facilities such as computers, storage devices and projectors which they need for preparing and teaching their lessons using computer animation.
2. Computer animation should be adopted in the chemistry curriculum delivery in all public secondary schools. This will help to foster interest of students in the study of the subject.

3. Since many chemistry teachers are not very familiar with computer animation and its benefits, conferences, seminars and workshops should be organized by relevant professional bodies to educate them on computer animation.

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